

OUR EXPERIENCE IN TREATING WORKING AGE PATIENTS WITH FEMORAL NECK FRACTURES

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Annatation. In this article, the authors describe the concept of “biological” osteosynthesis of femoral neck fractures in patients of working age. In 67 patients, combined metal-osteoplastic osteosynthesis was performed. The technique involved decentralized paired placement of implants in the femoral neck, combining elements of compression (screws) and neutral cortical autograft from the fibula) osteosynthesis. Due to this, optimal conditions were achieved for drainage of accumulated blood and reparative osteogenesis. The results were monitored over a period of 9 months to 3 years. Positive outcomes of surgical treatment were observed in 94% of patients.

Key words: femoral neck, “biological” osteosynthesis, bone grafting, cortical autograft, compression screws.

Introduction. Treatment of patients with femoral neck fractures remains an urgent and insufficiently solved problem of modern traumatology and orthopedics. This is due, on the one hand, to the epidemiology of the disease. According to publications from Scandinavian countries, from 1960 to 1985 the incidence of hip fractures in developed countries doubled. [3, 4]. Judging by the literature data, the frequency of fractures of this location in people of working age ranges from 25 to 33.2%, and there is a tendency to “rejuvenate” the pathology [2]. In Hungary, 1:5000 people experience femoral neck fractures annually, with 46% of patients under 50 years of age [5]. On the other hand, the anatomical and functional features of the proximal femur often do not allow adequate organ-preserving surgical intervention, which is one of the reasons for unsatisfactory outcomes after osteosynthesis (27-47.5%).

Many years of research have proven the indisputable advantages of early surgical treatment tactics. In patients under 60 years of age, preference is given to osteosynthesis [9]. The search continues for the most optimal ways to perform it and reduce the invasiveness of the intervention. There are controversial views on the advisability of bone grafting when performing primary osteosynthesis.

The causes of “local” complications are being studied, among which one of the most common is avascular necrosis of the femoral head, which occurs against the background of

impaired blood supply.

In the clinic, total ischemia never occurs. The vessels of the ligament of the femoral head always remain intact, and the thicker free part of the caudal network is not affected in most cases. Their anastomoses provide blood supply during reposition, surgery and consolidation of the fracture after osteosynthesis, performed several days after the injury [5]. In this regard, maintaining the integrity of the central structures of the neck and head of the femur is one of the main conditions for biological osteosynthesis, which provides for a decentralized arrangement of paired non-massive fixators in the most durable bone structures of the neck and head of the femur.

Discussion continues regarding the main cause of the formation of avascular necrosis of the femoral head after a neck fracture.

A number of authors see the problem in compression of the vascular network due to increased intra-articular pressure caused by intra-articular hematoma [7]. However, intra-articular pressure does not reach the values of mean arterial pressure even with a tense hematoma, and can only limit blood supply [6]. An intra-articular hematoma is more likely to interrupt the venous outflow from the head of the femur, since the walls of the veins are thinner, and their tone and venous pressure are lower.

The role of hemarthrosis has not been clarified. So, with pronounced displacement of fragments, the joint capsule ruptures, and therefore intra-articular pressure cannot increase. The incidence of late avascular necrosis is highest in the group of patients with Garden III-IV fractures [8,9]. This is explained by the fact that the disturbance of blood supply also has an intraosseous component (3). At the level of the fracture, the capillary network between the trabeculae and trabeculae is ruptured and, thus, impedes the outflow of blood from the head, as a result of which intraosseous pressure increases, which leads to the development of microscopic compartment syndrome [10].

Thus, in the process of performing organ-preserving surgical intervention, measures aimed at improving the outflow of blood from the femoral head and reducing intraosseous pressure are advisable.

Purpose of the work: development, justification and clinical application of the concept of “biological” osteosynthesis for fractures of the femoral neck in patients of working age,

Material and methods. The material is based on observation of 47 patients with fractures of the femoral neck, who underwent osteosynthesis in the traumatology department of the Khorezm branch of the Russian Research Center for Medical Sciences in the period from 2018 to 2022.

The gender and age composition of the study population is presented as follows:

In groups under 50 years of age, male patients predominate, which is associated with unusual circumstances of injury. In groups over 50 years old - female patients whose fracture occurred due to postmenopausal osteoporosis. In 27 (57.4%) cases, the injury was of a domestic nature, in 3 (6.3%) - at work, in 17 (36.1%) - on the street. 27 patients had a fracture of the left hip, and 20 had a fracture of the right.

When analyzing radiographs, transcervical fractures were noted in 44 (93.6%) cases, subcapital fractures in 3 (6.3%) cases. Based on the Pauwels classification: 33 (70%) patients are classified as stage I, 14 (29.7%) - stage II.

All surgical interventions were performed under spinal anesthesia in a closed, extra-articular manner.

The closed reposition technique developed in the clinic included the following points. A 15 cm high cushion was placed under the sacrum and the patient's legs were fixed to the orthopedic table - this prevented pathological anteversion in the area of the fracture. External rotation of the foot was carried out, facilitating the separation of fragments along the length and angle. Then, traction was applied along the axis with correction of displacement from neck fractures along the width and length. Next, two or three times internal and external rotation of the foot were performed alternately with final fixation of the limb in a position of internal rotation of 30-40°. This ensured correction of fragments in the case of a comminuted fracture of the femoral neck (according to our observations, this occurred in 65% of cases). The state of achieved reposition was determined using an X-ray machine with an electron-optical converter (EOC).

The collection of bone material for plastic surgery was carried out by exposing the middle third of the fibula from an external approach, followed by a vertical cut along the long axis of the bone in the oblique sagittal plane.

The advantage of this technique was the following:

- only the outer surface of the fibula was skeletonized; throughout the rest of the length, the periosteum remained intact;
- there was no need for invasion into the interosseous space where the venous plexuses are located;
- partial resection along the length made it possible to obtain a transplant of sufficient size

without compromising the integrity of the fibula;

-the triangular configuration of the graft ensured its stability in the canal, as it excluded rotational micromovements, which had a positive effect on its transformation;

the bone marrow canal, open along the length of the graft, ensured drainage of the accumulated blood after its insertion.

The next stage was a linear external approach to the trochanteric region of the thigh. Three wires were inserted parallel to each other into the neck and head of the femur, positioning them so that an isosceles triangle was formed in the cross section, with its apex facing the greater trochanter. The first wire was inserted as far as possible along the upper contour of the femoral neck, then two were inserted as close as possible and along the Adams arc, controlling their location using an X-ray machine with an electron-optical converter (EOC).

Next, three channels were formed along the spokes using a hollow drill. The first to insert was a proximal compression screw, ensuring a valgus position of the fragments. Then a distal screw was inserted, with the help of which compression was achieved in the fracture zone. A cortical graft was inserted posterior to the distal screw.

The advantage of the proposed method was the “biological” fixation of a short proximal fragment of the femur, eliminating rotational and varus displacements due to three implants. Compression of the fracture zone was achieved using two parallel inserted screws, located at the maximum distance from each other and from the center of the neck (without disturbing the blood circulation of the central zone) in the optimally strong structures of the proximal femur fragment. A cortical bone graft located along the lower contour of the neck, in addition to additional fixation, provided closure of the defect in case of a comminuted fracture, drainage of accumulated blood from the femoral head and created optimal conditions for reparative osteogenesis.

In the postoperative period, immobilization of the operated leg was carried out using a derotational boot. On the second day, the patient was sat up in bed, and on days 3–4 he was verticalized and taught to walk with the help of crutches.

Dynamic x-ray examination of the hip joint was carried out at 12, 24, 36 and 48 weeks. 12 weeks after the operation, in the absence of resorption in the fracture zone, separation of bone fragments and migration of structures, which indicated positive dynamics in terms of consolidation, the patient was allowed a dosed load on the forefoot. After 24 weeks, if there were

signs of fracture consolidation, walking with weight bearing on the operated limb was allowed; first with one crutch, then, in the absence of pain syndrome and trophic disorders - with an orthopedic cane, then - without it.

Results and discussion. Long-term results were monitored over a period of 9 months to 3 years in 47 patients. An original three-level system for grading results was used: “good”, “satisfactory”, “unsatisfactory”.

They were assessed based on clinical manifestations characterizing the degree of dysfunction and the degree of its compensation, which in our opinion is important, since the latter for patients is a determining component of the quality of life after injury and surgical intervention and reflects the degree of expression of the body's adaptive and compensatory capabilities, and, consequently, the level of development of adaptive reactions.[1]

Good treatment results were observed in 40 patients (89.5%), satisfactory - in 3 (6.3%), unsatisfactory - in 4 (8.5%). Among the unsatisfactory results, 1 case was associated with a technical error in performing osteosynthesis, when Reposition was not achieved during the intervention. Within 3 months, cervical lysis and screw migration occurred. The patient was readmitted to the hospital, where the structures were removed and total hip replacement was performed. In 2 cases, an unsatisfactory outcome was noted due to the fault of patients who received repeated injury - a fall on the hip joint. As a result, in one case there was a fracture of the graft and migration of the screw, in another - against the background of outward migration of the screws, varus displacement of the proximal fragment of the femur. In both cases, total cemented hip replacement was performed. In 1 patient with a subcapital fracture, Garden IV, screw migration was noted 12 weeks after the intervention. We consider the main reason to be the characteristics of the fracture - subcapital; total hip arthroplasty was performed.

In the group of satisfactory results, all 3 patients showed consolidation of the femoral neck fracture without signs of avascular necrosis of the head (follow-up period 2-3 years). One patient still had pain in the operated limb caused by varicose veins. In 2 patients, after examination by a neurologist, they came to the conclusion that it was related to osteochondrosis of the lumbar spine.

Summary. The method of surgical treatment, implemented in the light of the concept of biological osteosynthesis, providing for a decentralized paired arrangement of non-massive fixators in the femoral neck, combining elements of compression (screws) and neutral (cortical graft) osteosynthesis, made it possible to achieve positive results. results in 89.5% of patients, due to strong “gentle” fixation, creation of conditions for drainage of accumulated blood and reparative osteogenesis.

LITERATURE:

1. Karev D.B. Osteosynthesis with compression screws as an option for surgical treatment of

- patients with medial fractures of the femur / D.B. Karev, B.A. Karev, S.I. Boltrukevich, A.E. Gorbachev // News of surgery. - Vitebsk. - 2009. - No. 3. -WITH. 96-102.
2. Karev B.A. On the issue of treatment of patients with femoral neck fractures in young and middle age/BA Karev, S.I. Boltrukevich, Mahmud-ul-Hassan, Ashur Shokri Zake [and others] // Mater. V11 Congress of Traumatologists and Orthopedists of the Republic of Belarus. - Minsk, 2002. -S. 181-183.
 3. Yusupova I.A. Results of surgical treatment of injuries of the hip joint //Astana medical journals.2023.-T.116. pp. 22-25.
 4. Yusupova I.A. Surgical treatment of hip joint injuries. //Journal of Clinical and Theoretical Medicine. -2021. No.6.-P.48-50Arnold C.C. Fracture of The femoral neck II. Relative importance of primary vascular damage and surgical procedure lor the development of necrosis of the femoral head / C.C. Arnoldi, H. Linderholm //Clin. Orthop,-1977. - Vol. 129. -P. 217-222
 5. Drake, J.K. Intracapsular pressure and hemarthrosis following femoral neck fracture/ J.K Drake, M.H. Meyers// Clin. Orthop. - 1984. - Vol. 182.-R 172-176.
 6. Manninger, J. Internal fixation of femoral neck fractures / J.Manninger, U.Bosch, P.Cserhati (et al.] //: An atlas.- Springer-Verlag /Wien, 2007,-310 c,
 7. Maruenda, J J. Intracapsular hip pressure after femoral neck fracture/ J.I. Maruenda, C. Barrios, F. Gomar // Clin. Orthop, 1997. - Vol, 340.-P. 172-180.
 8. Strmqvist, B. Intracapsular pressures In undisplaced fractures of the femoral neck/ B. Strmqvist, L,T. Nilsson, N. Egund [et al,] // J. Bone Joint Surg, 1988. – Vol. 70-B. - P. 192194.
 9. Thorngren, K. Swedish multi center hip fracture study/ K.Thorngrem M. Berglund-R d n, T, Dolk[etaL]//Acta Orthop. Scand. 1990,-Vol. 237, №61. - P.53-54,
 10. Rakhimov, Bakhtiyar; Rakhimova, Feroza; Sobirova, Sabokhat; Allaberganov, Odilbek; ,Mathematical Bases Of Parallel Algorithms For The Creation Of Medical Databases,InterConf,,,2021,
 11. Rakhimov, Bakhtiyar Saidovich; Rakhimova, Feroza Bakhtiyarovna; Sobirova, Sabokhat Kabulovna; Kuryazov, Furkat Odilbekovich; Abdirimova, Dilnoza Boltabaevna; ,Review And Analysis Of Computer Vision Algorithms,The American Journal of Applied sciences,3,5,245-250,2021,
 12. Saidovich, Rakhimov Bakhtiyar; Bakhtiyarovich, Saidov Atabek; Farkhodovich, Babajanov Boburbek; Ugli, Karimov Doston Alisher; Qizi, Musaeva Mukhtasar Zayirjon; ,Analysis And Using of the Features Graphics Processors for Medical Problems,Texas Journal of

- Medical Science,7,,105-110,2022,
13. Rakhimov, BS; ,Russian "Information technologies in medical education",METHODS OF SCIENCE Scientific and practical journal,12,,25-7,2017,
 14. Rakhimov, BS; Ismoilov, OI; Ozodov, RO; ,Russian "Software and automation of forensic examination",METHODS OF SCIENCE Scientific and practical journal,11,,28-30,2017,
 15. Saidovich, Rakhimov Bakhtiyar; Kabulovna, Sobirova Sabokhat; Bakhtiyarovna, Rakhimova Feroza; Akbarovna, Allayarova Asal; Bakhtiyarovich, Saidov Atabek; ,ANALYSIS OF THE GRAPHICS PROCESSORS FOR MEDICAL PROBLEMS,PEDAGOGS jurnali,11,4,167-177,2022,
 16. Allaberganov, Odilbek R; Rakhimov, Bakhtiyar S; Sobirova, Sabokhat K; Rakhimova, Feroza B; Saidov, Atabek B; ,Problem for medical system with infinite zone potential in the half line,AIP Conference Proceedings,2647,1,,2022,AIP Publishing
 17. Rakhimov, Bakhtiyar Saidovich; Saidov, Atabek Bakhtiyarovich; Shamuratova, Inabat Ismailovna; Ibodullaeva, Zarnigor Ollayor Qizi; ,Architecture Processors in Data Base Medical Problems,International Journal on Orange Technologies,4,10,87-90,2022,Research Parks Publishing
 18. Rakhimov, Bakhtiyar Saidovich; Saidov, Atabek Bakhtiyarovich; Allayarova, Asal Akbarovna; ,Using the Model in Cuda and Opencl for Medical Signals,International Journal on Orange Technologies,4,10,84-86,2022,Research Parks Publishing
 19. Saidovich, Rakhimov Bakhtiyar; Musaevich, Yakubov Durumboy; Bakhtiyarovich, Saidov Atabek; Qizi, Saidova Zarina Bakhtiyar; ,ANALYSIS OF THE DEVICE FEATURES OF GENERAL-PURPOSE PROGRAMMABLE GRAPHICS PROCESSORS,CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND COMPUTER SCIENCES,4,1,100-103,2023,
 20. Касымов, СС; Зайнидинов, ХН; Рахимов, БС; ,Применение базисных сплайнов для предварительной обработки экспериментальных данных,"Тезисы докл. XVI-Международная научная конф., Санкт",,,,2003,
 21. Рахимов, БС; ,Проектирование спецпроцессов для обработки сигналов на основе матричной диаграммы занятости,Научно-технический журнал Ферганского политехнического института,4,,31,2003,
 22. Рахимов, БС; ,"Кусочно-полиномиальные методы на основе функций Уолша, Актуальные вопросы в области технических и социально-экономических наук",Межвузовский сб. научн. трудов. Ташкент,1,,42,2006,

23. Rakhimov, BS; Allabeganov, OR; Saidov, AB; ,Processor means for the spectral analysis of medical signals on the of polynomial walsh bases epra,International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD),5,7,10-11,2020,
24. Saidovich, Rakhimov Bakhtiyar; Gafurovich, Bekchanov Bakhtiyar; Alimovna, Jumaniyazova Tupajon; Bakhtiyarovich, Saidov Atabek; ,Processor Architectures in Data Base Problems,Procedia of Engineering and Medical Sciences,,43-47,2022,